

Mapping Economic Diversification in the Arab World

HOW MUCH INERTIA IS THERE?

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Section 1. Introduction.

This paper has seven sections. The first section evaluates and expands on the available literature on economic diversification and later, it develops a strong understanding of what truly economic diversification is, outlining the multitudinous nature of economic diversification. The following section is based on research, and scholarly and empirical findings to justify why economic diversification is more than a tool and not a policy and how it is relevant to the Arab World. These findings help to identify the multiple dimensions of economic diversification in the Arab World for mapping the diversification which is the purpose of this paper.

Eventually, section four highlights some of the key points of how economic diversification can be measured by generating a composite index and how it contributes to mapping the diversification in the Arab World. The last two sections are focused on the results of the composite index that are based on the weighted average method and essential interpretations of the index. Leaving the final part for the conclusion based on the available evidence.

Keywords. *Economic Diversification. Mapping. Dimensions of Diversification. Arab World. Peak Oil Demand. Resource Rents. Fuel Exports. Merchandise Exports. Diversified Political Actors. Fiscal Diversification. Industry Diversification. Adjacent Product Space. Composite Index. Weighted Average Method.*

Section 2. What is economic diversification? Is it only policy making? Literature is wide and understanding crucial aspects is important.

Economic diversification has broad literature and the definition is quite vague. Before we analyse economic diversification in the Arab World, it is crucial to look into the available literature provided by different established institutions and research. This will help to take positions on the topic and highlight key shreds of evidence. Eventually, bringing together the multi-dimensions of economic diversification to measure the effects in the different Arab countries is the aim. So to arrive there, evaluation and study of the literature are pivotal.

A well-positioned economy with diversified sectors is more resilient to threats posed by external technological, climate policy changes and market volatility shocks¹. For the Arab World, there is a renewed sense of priority around economic diversification as the concept of “peak oil demand” is gaining unanimity among scholars, institutions, policymakers and company executives². Economic diversification is identified as the method of redistributing an economy's income from a single source to a variety of sources originating from an expanding number of industries and marketplaces³. Though the merits of economic diversification are known by many institutions and scholars, the reality is often quite different. Many political institutes such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank Group (WBG), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), United Nations Climate Change (UNFCC) and World Trade Organization (WTO) have laid out a similar sketch to pursue economic diversification.

A sketch that assists in understanding the overall picture of economic diversification can be seen below in Figure A.

Economic diversification is often called a policy, however, it is more than a tool and not just a policy.

¹ World Bank Group, *Economic Diversification: Lessons learnt from practice*, Chapter 5, p.139.

² Sen, B. F. (April 2020). Chapter 5, Economic Diversification in Arab Oil-Exporting Countries in the Context of Peak Oil and the Energy Transition. In G. L. Editors - Ashraf Mishrif, *When Can Oil Economies Be Deemed Sustainable?* (p. 74). London, UK: palgrave macmillan.

³ Nations, U. (2023, February 22). *Economic Diversification*. Retrieved from United Nations Climate Change: <https://unfccc.int/topics/resilience/resources/economic-diversification>.

Figure A. The sketch of pursuing economic diversification as portrayed by many political institutions.

To understand this aspect, it is fundamental to study what factors constitute economic diversification. It is easier to diversify to an adjacent product in an economy that is closer to the existing product space. In other words, economic diversification is path dependent⁴. This highlights the challenges and risks posed by resource-rich countries that are dependent on natural resources as the primary source of income. For example, crude oil and petroleum sectors cannot be diversified into other various products and industries since the product space is very limited. Wide-reaching dependence on natural resources is vulnerable to global price fluctuations in an economy. Recent major global events, such as the Covid-19 pandemic, the Russia-Ukraine war and climate change policies have resulted in colossal changes in overall global demand for various products, services and industries and macroeconomic volatility. Research also shows evidence that even though the demand for non-commodities can be substantially volatile due to the resource sector, relative prices can remain steady and shocks can be better absorbed if a country has a strong non-resource tradable sector⁵. Another empirical regularity is the positive correlation between diversified exports and a country’s total GDP⁶. Therefore, exports of a country make a relevant dimension to mapping economic diversification

⁴ Freire, C. (2017). Economic Diversification: Explaining the pattern of diversification in the global economy and its implications for fostering diversification in the poorer countries. *DESA Working Paper No. 150, T/ESA/2017/DWP/150, United Nations*, p. 2.

⁵ Hausmann and Rigobon (2003). An Alternative Interpretation of the ‘Resource-Curse’: Theory and Policy Implications. *NBER working paper series, w9424. National Bureau of Economic Research*.

⁶ Freire (n 4).

in an economy. Thus, mapping various distributions across commodity and non-commodity exports helps to understand the picture of economic diversification.

Other two key dimensions of economic diversification are diversification of government revenues, taxes and fiscal policies and diversified political actors. According to empirical findings and research, an increase in political power and resource inheritances are directly related which results in bad state behaviour and policies⁷. Therefore, after evaluating the available literature on economic diversification a picture can be made clear to map economic diversification in the Arab World (see Figure B).

Diversification is a tool not policy

Figure B. Highlighting why diversification is made of many aspects and it is not just policy making.

Section 3. Outlining multitudinous nature of economic diversification. Profiling dimensions for mapping the diversification in the Arab World.

The character of economic diversification is now clear so that we can profile the multiple dimensions together to map diversification in the Arab World. It makes sense to bring together different dimensions or economic indicators to capture the effects of an economy rather than studying them individually. As it turns out that

⁷ Robinson, Torvik and Verdier (2006). Political foundations of resource curse. *Journal of Development Economics* 79 (2006) 447 – 468 Harvard University, p. 1-2.

there are interdependencies and a composite index can best help to measure these different factors that contribute to stable economic diversification. For this paper, we have identified that a composite index can be generated by clustering data from relevant indicators and making one meaningful index later to interpret. There are various models and clustering methods in mathematics and statistics, for this paper we have used the ‘weighted average method’ to generate a composite index. Every data collection has some assumptions and shortcomings, so it is correct to state that the data collected for different indicators for this paper, published by various established economic institutions have some limitations too.

For this paper, we have identified the following indicators as the multiple dimensions of economic diversification to map the effects in the Arab World: Resource rents, industry – value-added, manufacturing – value-added, all as a percentage of nominal GDP, exports and fuel exports as a percentage of nominal GDP, merchandise trade as a percentage of nominal GDP, total revenue and tax revenue as a percentage of nominal GDP.

Resource rents, industry – value added, and manufacturing – value added account for output-diversification indicators for this index. Exports, fuel exports and merchandise trade account for trade-diversification indicators. Whereas, total revenue and tax revenue account for fiscal and policy diversification indicators. It is important to note that there are other models and methods to generate an index to measure the performance of a policy and diversified political actors. However, since we are using the weighted average method for measuring the performance of indicators which are all percentages of nominal GDP, the resulting index will capture the overall diversification in an economy. This brings some limitations. The limitations are as follows:

- It doesn’t measure in-depth the effects of various diversification policies but captures the total revenue and tax revenue generated in a fiscal year from different industries and economic actors.
- Performances of policies and different political actors are interpreted after the composite index is generated as against during the index is generated.

- Weights for weighted average calculation are decided by benchmarking the performance of the most diversified economy in the world for given indicators. In this case, we have identified the United States as a benchmark.
- The data collected for each indicator stated above is sourced from World Bank Open Data which has its own limitations.

Section 4. Why an index is generated? What does it contribute? Measuring economic diversification is possible using the resulting composite index.

Figure C gives an overall impression of what is our choice of indicators to summarize Section 3.

Dimensions of diversification can be profiled – the Arab World

- Resource rents, industry, manufacturing – value added as percentage of GDP
- Exports and fuel exports as percentage of GDP
- Merchandise trade as percentage of GDP
- Total revenue and tax revenue as percentage of GDP

Figure C. Indicators chosen for generating the composite index.

A composite index measures all the effects of the indicators that feed it based on the type of method to generate it. The Weighted Average Method attributes different weights to each chosen indicator and that helps to scale the performance of indicators together for each country. Since every indicator is of a different mathematical scale, we converted every indicator as a percentage of nominal GDP for the purpose of calculation.

To see the summary of the contributions of a composite index and why this method is appropriate see Figure D.

The data for calculating composite index is taken from World Bank Open Data. To see the data in detail check the Appendix.

Measuring it is possible and index generation is right approach

Analysing dimensions together is better to capture effects and interdependencies.

Benchmarking and comparing performance using weighted average method.

Results will be ranked from 1-100.

The resulting composite index will be interpreted.

Figure D. Summary of composite index generation.

Section 5. Resulting composite index for the Arab World. Rankings.

Figure E. Resulting composite index 2023.

Figure F. Resulting rankings based on the index generated for the Arab World.

Section 6. Interpretation of the resulting composite index. Is there inertia or not?

Based on the composite index that we calculated, the following interpretations can be made:

- Diversified manufacturing, exports and merchandise trade with adjacent products are positively correlated to economic diversification.
- High resource rents, concentrated activities in the area of mining, and natural resource-based sectors and high fuel exports are negatively correlated to economic diversification.
- Positive changes in diversification and fiscal policies, diversified institutions and political actors affect the total revenue and tax revenue of different sectors. Thus, government reforms are necessary and private sectors are positively correlated to diversification.
- Structural change from natural resources is imperative to tackle “peak oil demand” that is set to happen earlier than expected within the next five years.
- The Arab World is performing very low as compared to the benchmark and there is inertia.

Section 7. Conclusion – based on the composite index results.

Saudi Arabia, Oman and Bahrain are the top three diversified countries in the Arab World according to the index while the United Arab Emirates is at the bottom as compared to the other Arab countries. The main reason behind these rankings is that UAE has the highest fuel exports in the Arab World and the concentration of activities in resource-based sectors is relatively very high. Also, the total revenue generated by UAE is not diversified compared to Saudi Arabia and other better-diversified countries.

The Arab World is far behind in economic diversification compared to the performance of the benchmark. This highlights the fact that there is indeed inertia in the Arab World. Economic diversification in the Arab World is more of a political challenge than an economic one. The pivotal reason behind this is reflected by the empirical regularity that the political structure in the Arabic World is not diversified and there are no well-established institutions to balance the scenarios. As there is direct a correlation between resource windfalls and a rise in the value of political power, it is thus clear that the long political inheritances in the Arab countries based on bloodlines and non-transparent bureaucracies are one of the biggest hurdles to economic diversification in the Arab World.

Abbreviations.

IMF – International Monetary Fund

WBG – World Bank Group

WTO – World Trade Organization

UNDP – United Nations Development Programme

UNFCCC – United Nations Climate Change

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Appendix.

Economic Diversification in the Arab World: Composite Index 2023 (Calculation Weighted Average)

Table 1.1

Series			Output Diversification Variables		
Arab Countries (Benchmarking US indicators)	Year	Real GDP (in billions USD)	Resource rents as percentage of GDP (in %)	Industry value added as percentage of GDP (in %)	Manufacturing value added as percentage of GDP (in %)
United Arab Emirates	2021	415,020,000,000	12%	48%	10%
Saudi Arabia	2021	833,540,000,000	18%	46%	13%
Qatar	2021	179,680,000,000	15%	60%	9%
Iraq	2021	207,890,000,000	32%	54%	2%
Kuwait	2021	105,960,000,000	32%	45%	7%
Oman	2021	88,190,000,000	21%	51%	9%
Bahrain	2021	38,870,000,000	9%	45%	20%
Unites States	2021	23,320,000,000,000	0.40%	18%	11%
Weights			20%	5%	8%

Table 1.2

Series			Trade Diversification Variables		
Arab Countries (Benchmarking US indicators)	Year	Real GDP (in billions USD)	Exports of goods and services as percentage of GDP (in %)	Fuel exports as percentage of GDP (in %)	Merchandise trade as percentage of GDP (in %)
United Arab Emirates	2021	415,020,000,000	96%	72%	186%
Saudi Arabia	2021	833,540,000,000	34%	26%	52%
Qatar	2021	179,680,000,000	59%	41%	64%
Iraq	2021	207,890,000,000	38%	42%	73%
Kuwait	2021	105,960,000,000	53%	55%	64%
Oman	2021	88,190,000,000	53%	17%	86%
Bahrain	2021	38,870,000,000	73%	17%	94%
Unites States	2021	23,320,000,000,000	11%	1%	20%
Weights			10%	30%	9%

Table 1.3

Series			Fiscal and Revenue Diversification Variables	
Arab Countries (Benchmarking US indicators)	Year	Real GDP (in billions USD)	Total revenue as percentage of GDP - excluding grants (in %)	Tax revenue as percentage of GDP (in %)
United Arab Emirates	2021	415,020,000,000	6%	0.70%
Saudi Arabia	2021	833,540,000,000	30%	8.60%
Qatar	2021	179,680,000,000	36%	
Iraq	2021	207,890,000,000	39%	1.30%
Kuwait	2021	105,960,000,000	44%	1.50%
Oman	2021	88,190,000,000	1%	3.80%
Bahrain	2021	38,870,000,000	27%	4.20%
Unites States	2021	23,320,000,000,000	18%	9.90%
Weights			13%	5%

Table 1.4

Series			Weighted Average Results (Least diversified has highest percentage)		Ranking	Index
Arab Countries (Benchmarking US indicators)	Year	Real GDP (in billions USD)				
United Arab Emirates	2021	415,020,000,000		54%	7	46%
Saudi Arabia	2021	833,540,000,000		27%	2	73%
Qatar	2021	179,680,000,000		35%	4	65%
Iraq	2021	207,890,000,000		37%	5	63%
Kuwait	2021	105,960,000,000		43%	6	57%
Oman	2021	88,190,000,000		26%	1	74%
Bahrain	2021	38,870,000,000		30%	3	70%
Unites States	2021	23,320,000,000,000		8%		
Weights				Total = 100%		Benchmark 92%